

**BENEFITS OF INTERGRATED WASTE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES
FOR THE PRODUCTION OF SUSTAINABLE ENERGY (BIOGAS) IN
PUBLIC BUILDING**

BY

Sani Abdulrahman Tolani¹ Abdullateef Abass Isola², Atiku Umar Faruk³.
Building Technology, Directorate of Environmental Programmes, Waziri Umaru Federal
Polytechnic Birnin
Kebbi, Kebbi State Nigeria.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Sani Abdulrahman Tolani
Building Technology, Directorate of Environmental Programmes,
Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic Birnin
Kebbi, Kebbi State Nigeria.
¹tolaniabdulrahman@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Biogas is a mixture of gases, primarily consisting of methane and carbon dioxide produced from agricultural waste, manure, municipal waste, plant, sewage, green waste and food waste. It is a renewable energy source that produces clean methane gas and fertilizer as the two biproduct. The research estimate the use of 200kg of fresh cow dung from Birnin Kebbi Abature, 1,000 liters of clean water, neatly washed into a digester containing 2,000 Liters space, connected to a gas tube of size 2m³/psi, 100mm inlet and outlet pipe (6 bar tick), 2 gas valves of 100mm diameter, 8 pvc connector adapter of 100mm diameter, 4 rubber nipples of 100mm, 0.5m flexible steel pipe, 3m poly-varec chloride (PVC) flexible polyester service gas pipe, 10kg adhesive (Resin and Hardener), 60 inches length of hose pipe, gas pressure meter, clips, screws, block work (blocks, sand, cement, stone), and 3 set of filtering process (Chlorine, Calcium and Sodium-Oxide). The process was carried out in an air tight ??? of cow dungs and water solution for a period of sixty days (60 days) before generating methane gas of 10m³ psi of raw methane gas which was used for cooking when channelled from a 2m³ to a gas burner for a period of 20 hours. The concept is termed waste – to – energy, which addresses sustainability problems such as reduction of environmental pollution, recycling waste for energy generation (biogas) and transmutation into bio- fertilizer (liquid) through an anaerobic digestion process. The implementation of waste treatment plant in public environment will help to reduce greenhouse gases (GHG), reduce cost of cooking gas and farming fertilizer as farm input for healthy living just to mention but few practiced in Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State Nigeria.

Keywords: waste management, generate energy, biogas (clean methane).

INTRODUCTION

The Kebbi kingdom was first established by Muhammad Kanta at Suraye as early as the sixteenth century, in 1515AD. Around the seventeenth century the political activities of the kingdom of Kebbi under the successive rulers after Kanta, shifted to the town of Birnin Kebbi (12.43180N,

4.19560E) under the leadership of Sarkin Kabi Tommo, the present day seat of Gwandu Emirate and capital city of Kebbi State in the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Kebbi is a state in North West Nigeria with its capital at Birnin Kebbi. The State was created out of a part of Sokoto State on 27th August, 1991. Kebbi State is bordered by Sokoto State to the North, Niger State to the South, Zamfara State to the East. Dosso region in the Republic of Niger to the West and Benin republic to the Southwest (Mukhtar, 2016).

Animal waste is the waste generated from various activities such as blood during slaughtering, and the associated waste during the meat butchering. Energy is a driver of economic growth, obtained from various primary sources that are not limited to coal, petroleum, nuclear but also incorporates renewable sources from wind, solar and biomass. Of these, the most widely used source is the non-renewable fossil fuel which account for more than 80% of global primary energy consumption with its attendant environmental pollution (Duerr, Cruden & McDonald 2018). Nigeria is not left out from such immense dependence on fossil fuel. A country endowed with primary energy resource with a record of the world's tenth largest reserves of crude oil estimated to be about 36 billion barrels (about 4.896 billion tons) of oil in 2016, is yet to attain sustainable development with resultant effect on the environment. The increasing concern for environmental health, eco-friendly waste management and sustainable energy production constitute the focus of many trade bodies, regulatory agencies, states and countries of the world. Energy efficiency and renewable energy are two key components of sustainable energy that provide significant environmental benefits. Promoting circular economy in the surroundings of an organic fraction of municipal solid waste through anaerobic digestion treatment plant for producing biproducts of gas and liquid production with large impact and economic factors (Abad, Avila, Vincent & Front, 2019).

Nigeria is a well populated country in Africa with significant resources of organic waste. Rapid urbanization, industrialization and agricultural activities have created environmental concern such as environmental pollution from municipal, industrial and agro-allied waste. Waste, an output of any operational system, which has continued to grow with more attention to an effective waste disposal management system. No doubt, there has been infinitesimal prospect into waste to energy technology (WTE) as a waste management strategy (Akhaton, Obanor & Ugege, 2017). This approach embodies the concept of the four R's, such as reduce, re-use, recycle and renewable energy which has generally been accepted as a useful principle for waste handling (Kothari, 2014). Waste-to-energy technology has been a viable waste management strategy in establishing sustainable waste disposal, delivery of renewable energy and providing better end products such as biogas generation and farm manure in comparison to other disposal methods (landfills or incineration). Hence biogas, a waste-to-energy strategy, do not only provide renewable energy in the form of heat, electricity, fuel and methane gas for cooking from low/ negative value organic waste (Kothari, *et al.*, 2008). The waste normally includes; solid, liquid and gaseous materials that accumulates with time.

According to Okey, et al, (2013), waste management which generally involves the collection, transfer, treatment, recycling, resources recovery and disposal of waste in any location. The major problem caused by wastes to the environment is pollution characterized by various types of waste, which must be effectively managed through appropriate reduction, reuse and/or recycled practices in other to maintain a clean municipal environment (Dauda & Osita, 2009). The management of municipal waste emerged as one of the most serious problems facing environmental protection in developing countries in Africa and some parts of the world. In most of these countries including Nigeria, Municipal Waste Management involves just the collection and transfer of waste to land fill or dump site with little or no conversion practices (Okey, *et al.*, 2013). The point in the

transition at which WTE becomes relevant is in the resource recovery stage as opined by Akhator *et al.*, (2017). It is a versatile energy source that can significantly reduce the use of fossil fuels and consequently contribute to energy security, which is a global challenge (Abubakar & Ismail, 2012). The factors for consideration in the process include; feasibility, ease of use (social acceptance), education requirement, infrastructure needs, economics, a potential for pollution, GHG emissions, land use requirements and technology need for further development. Waste to energy (WTE) technologies have the potential to reduce the volume of the original waste by 90%, depending on the composition, by recovering otherwise lost energy and metals in MSW, thus providing a means of alternate/renewable energy and a reduction of society's use of precarious energy resources can be realized (Voelker, 2004; Wang, 2009; Kathiravale, 2008; Kothari, *et al.*, 2013). No doubt, the lack of necessary and adequate WTE technology in developing countries like Nigeria is still a dominant issue as there are no operating engineered landfills, bioreactors or large-scale ADs for the production of biogas. Therefore, resources that could potentially be harnessed and recovered for WTE are untapped through indiscriminate disposal in dump sites, which consequently impacts negatively on the environment (Duerr *et al.*, 2018).

This research therefore offer prospects through which solid waste, a potential source of anaerobic microorganisms could be harnessed for biogas production in the abattoir, especially in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State.

CURRENT PRACTICE AND PROBLEMS OF SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIA

Currently, the use of **Septic Tank/Cess Pool** in handling of sewage in Africa is being phased out as a result of the environmental impacts of inappropriate off-site disposal of untreated sludge dislodged from the tanks. Septic tank/Cess pool has become significant land-based sources of pollution with implications of poor sanitation and public-health related hazards. Evacuation of Sewage cost an average of about ₦50,000 to ₦100,000 per trip which also have tendency to devalue the worth of any facility.

According to Adelakun (2002), Biogas simply refers to gas produced by the biological breakdown /disintegration of organic matter in the absence of oxygen. Human solid waste, organic waste such as dead plant and animal material, animal dung, and kitchen waste can be converted into gaseous fuel known as the "Biogas. Biogas originates from biogenic material (i.e resulting from biological activities) and is a type of biofuel, which is generally used to describe secondary renewable fuels obtained by thermos chemical processing or the bioconversion of biomass especially carbonaceous waste material. Biogas is a gaseous fuel obtained from biomass by the process of anaerobic digestion or fermentation, when bacteria degrade biological material in the absence of oxygen. The in-feed or raw material to the biogas plant or bioreactor for the production of biogas includes:

- i. Manure (for example human excreta or cow dung)
- ii. Urban waste (garbage)
- iii. Green waste
- iv. Sewage
- v. Agricultural waste

Biogas comprises primarily of methane (CH₄), and carbon dioxide CO₂; and may have small amount of hydrogen sulphide (H₂S), moisture and siloxanes. The gases- methane, hydrogen and carbon monoxide (CO) can be combusted or oxidized with oxygen. The energy release allows a biogas to be used as a fuel. in any country especially Nigeria for any heating purpose, such as cooking. It can also be used in anaerobic digesters where it is typically used in a gas engine to convert the energy in the gas into electricity and heat. Just like the natural gas, the biogas can also be compressed and used to power motor vehicles. For example, in UK biogas is estimated to have

the potential of replacing around 17% of vehicle fuel. Being a renewable fuel, it qualifies for renewable energy subsidies in some parts of the world and can also be cleaned and upgraded to natural gas when it becomes bio-methane (Folarin, 2008).

Figure 1 Shows the cycle of how biogas is produced, sources of waste and usages.

Organic waste generation in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State

In order to have an in-depth knowledge of biogas, it is very vital to have a good understanding of organic waste, what they are, their examples, and their environmental impacts. An organic waste therefore, is anything that comes from plants or animals that is biodegradable, which implies that they are substances that will decay relatively quickly as a result of the action of bacteria and break down into elements such as carbon that are recycled naturally (Encarta Dictionaries, 2009).

Types of solid waste generated in Birnin Kebbi abattoir

Several types of organic waste generated include:

- i. Solid waste: Human waste (or human excreta) - the waste products of the human digestive system, menses, and human metabolism including urine and faeces.
- ii. Agri-food industries waste: These are very charged organic effluents and are potentially strong in methane. This includes the Fruit and vegetable by-products, and canteen waste (Ezekoye, 2006).
- iii. Green waste: Waste of the communities shearing of grass, sheets etc and have seasonal character.
- iv. Wastewater treatment plants sludge: These are divided into the Primary and secondary sludge.
- v. Grease: These could be obtained from restaurant vats of degreasing and are potentially strong in methane (Okeke, 2011).

Other examples of wastes are: Eggshells, rice, beans, cheese, bones, frozen refrigerated food, paper towels etc.

IMPACTS OF ORGANIC WASTE

According to Song (2004) Organic waste has both negative and positive impacts to the environment and its entire component (biotic and abiotic). The following are some specific areas of the impact of organic waste.

i. Contamination: Much of the land used for waste disposal cannot be reused in the future because of contamination. This occurs when rubbish in landfills is compressed and the air is squeezed out. The rubbish breaks down anaerobically (without oxygen), which means that acids are produced. The acids affect other rubbish items, such as plastic, to create a toxic mix known as leachate. Leachate collects at the bottom of landfills where then seeps into the ground water and from there into the waterways.

ii. Landfill Space: In many areas the land allocated to waste disposal is rapidly filling up. Approximately half of all household waste is organic. Most of this waste can be recycled through composting turning waste material into a rich soil supplement for use in your garden. By composting, not only can you help to reduce the amount of waste that goes into landfill but you can also help to reduce contamination and greenhouse gasses.

iii. Greenhouse Gases: As organic waste decomposes in landfill produces the greenhouse gases. Methane and carbon dioxide. These greenhouse gases contribute worldwide climate change. Most landfill gas is made up of 54% methane and 40% carbon dioxide. Methane is twenty-four times more damaging as a greenhouse gas than carbon dioxide. Scientists predict that climate change will impact on all our lives, especially in the areas of agriculture and human health (Tower Lonbard et al, 2012).

BENEFITS OF COMPOSITING

- i. Compost improves drainage in clay soils and helps sandy soils retain water (Tower, 2012)
- ii. Compost assists plant growth and disease resistance.
- iii. Compost also helps to absorb and filter runoff, protecting streams from erosion and pollution.
- iv. Composting reduces unwanted insects limiting the need for commercial herbicides or pesticides, therefore preventing runoff pollution (Wilkie, 2004)
- v. You won't have to bag and drag garden waste to the kerb for collection or pay to have it trucked to the tip.

COMPOSITION OF HUMAN SOLID WASTE

The composition of human solid waste is given in table 1.

	Faeces	Urine
amount	150-300 g/person/day	1-1,3 l/person/day
moisture content	66-80%	93-96%
dry matter	40-81 g/person/day	50-70 g/person/day
in the dry matter:		
organic compounds	88-97%	65-85%
N	5-7%	15-19%
P (as P₂O₅)	3-5,4%	2,5-5%
K (as K₂O)	1-2,5%	3,0-4,5%
C	40-55%	11-17%
Ca (as CaO)	4-5%	4,5-6%

Table 1: Showing the composition of human solid waste

BIOMASS

According to Lincoln, (2019), biomass is any organic matter-wood, crops, seaweed, animal wastes- that can be used as an energy source. Biomass is probably our oldest source of energy after the sun. For thousands of years, people have burned wood to heat their homes and cook their food. Biomass gets its energy from the sun. All organic matter contains stored energy from the sun. During a process called photosynthesis, sunlight gives plants the energy they need to convert water and carbon dioxide into oxygen and sugars. These sugars called carbohydrates, supply plants and the animals that eat plants with energy. As opined by Wilkie, (2003), biomass is a renewable energy source because its supplies are not limited since we can always grow trees and crops, and waste will always exist.

Types of Biomass

We use four types of biomass today-Wood and agricultural products, solid waste, landfill gas biogas, and alcohol fuels.

i. Wood and Agricultural Products: Most biomass used today is home grown energy. Wood-logs, chips, bark, and sawdust accounts for about 49 percent of biomass energy. But any organic matter can produce biomass energy. Other biomass sources include agricultural waste products like fruit pits and cocombs. Wood and wood waste, along with agricultural waste, are used to generate electricity. Much of the electricity is used by the industries making the waste; it is not distributed by utilities, it is cogenerated. Paper mills and saw mills use much of their waste products to generate steam and electricity for their use. However, since they use so much energy, they need to buy additional electricity from utilities (Boum, 2011). Increasingly, timber companies and companies involved with wood products are seeing the benefits of using their lumber scrub and sawdust for power generation. This saves disposal costs and, in some areas, may reduce the companies' utility bills. In fact, the pulp and paper industries rely on biomass to meet half of their energy needs. Other industries that use biomass include lumber producers, furniture manufacturers, agricultural businesses like nut and rice growers, and liquor producers.

ii. Solid Waste: Burning trash turns waste into a usable form of energy. One ton (2,000 pounds) of garbage contains about as much heat energy as 500 pounds of coal. Garbage is not all biomass; perhaps half of its energy content comes from plastics, which are made from petroleum and natural gas. Power plants that burn garbage for energy are called waste-to-energy plants. These plants generate electricity much as coal-fired plants do, except that combustible garbage-not coal-is the fuel used to fire their boilers. The electricity from garbage, costs more than that from coal and other energy sources. The main advantage of burning solid waste is that it reduces the amount of garbage dumped in landfills by 60 to 90 per cent, which in tum reduces the cost of landfill disposal. It also makes use of the energy in the garbage, rather than burying it in a landfill, where it remains unused.

iii. Landfill Gas: Landfill gas is a complex combination of different gases created by the action of microorganisms within a landfill, which is a carefully engineered depression in the ground (or built on top of the ground, resembling a football stadium) into which wastes are collected. The aim of having this landfill is to avoid any hydraulic (or water-related) connection between the wastes and the environment, most especially the ground water. Bacteria and fungi are not picky eaters. They eat dead plants and animals, causing them to rot or decay. A fungus on a rotting log is converting cellulose to sugars to feed itself. Although this process is slowed in a landfill, a substance called methane gas is still produced as the waste decays (Wolly, 2011). New regulations require landfills to collect methane gas for safety and environmental reasons. Methane gas is colourless and odourless, but it is not harmless. The gas can cause fires or explosions if it seeps into nearby homes and is united. Landfills can collect the methane gas, purify it, and use it as fuel. Methane, the main ingredient in natural gas, is a good energy source. Most gas furnaces and stoves use methane supplied by utility companies. In 2003, East Kentucky Power Cooperative began recovering methane from three landfills. The utility now uses the gas at five body fills to generate 16 megawatts of electricity enough to power 7,500-8,000 homes. Today, a small portion of landfill gas is used to provide energy most of which is burned off at the landfill. With today's low natural gas prices, this higher-priced biogas is rarely economical to collect. Methane, however, is a more powerful greenhouse gas than carbon dioxide. It is better to bum landfill methane and change it into carbon dioxide than release it into the atmosphere. Methane can also be produced using energy from agricultural and human wastes. Bio-digesters are airtight containers or pits lined with steel or bricks. Waste put into the containers is fermented without oxygen to produce a methane-rich gas. This gas can be used to produce electricity, or for cooking and lighting. It is a safe and clean-burning gas, producing little carbon monoxide and no smoke. Biogas digesters are inexpensive to build and maintain. They can be built as family-sized or community-sized units. They need moderate temperatures and moisture for the fermentation process to occur.

For developing countries, biogas digesters may be one of the best answers to many of their energy needs. They can help reverse the rampant deforestation caused by wood-burning, and can reduce: air pollution, fertilize over-used fields, and produce clean, safe energy for rural communities (Okeke, 2006).

Examples of biomass used as the raw materials for the production of biogas are shown in Figure.2 below.

Types of Biomass

Figure 2: Types of Biomass.

Almost half of the biomass used today comes from burning wood and wood scraps such as saw dust. More than one-thirds from biofuels, principally ethanol, that are used as a gasoline additive. The rest comes from crops, garbage, and landfill gas. Industries are the biggest user of biomass as over 51 percent of biomass is used by industries. Electric utilities use 11 percent of biomass for power generation as biomass produces 0.7 percent of the electricity we use. Transportation is the next biggest user of biomass, almost 24 percent of biomass is used by the transportation sector to produce ethanol and biodiesel while the residential sector uses 11 percent of the biomass supply.

Benefit of using biomass energy

Usually, we burn wood and use its energy for heating. Burning, however, is not the only way to convert biomass energy into a usable energy source. There are other four ways:

- i. **Fermentation:** There are several types of processes that can produce in alcohol (ethanol) from various plants, especially maize. The two most commonly used processes involve using yeast to ferment the starch in the plant to produce ethanol. One of the newest processes involves using enzymes to break down the cellulose in the plant trees, allowing more ethanol to be made from each plant, because all of the plant tissue is utilized, not just the starch.
- ii. **Burning:** We can burn biomass in waste-to-energy plants to produce steam for making electricity, or we can burn it to provide heat for industries and homes.
- iii. **Bacterial Decay:** Bacteria feed on dead plants and animals, producing methane. Methane is produced whenever organic material decays. Methane is the main ingredient in natural gas, the gas sold by natural gas utilities. Many landfills are recovering and using the methane gas produced by the garbage.
- iv. **Conversion:** Biomass can be converted into gas or liquid fuels by using chemicals or heat. In India, cow manure is converted to methane gas to produce electricity. Methane gas can also be converted to methanol, a liquid form of methane.

Effect of biomass and the environment

Environmentally, biomass has some advantages over fossil fuels such as coal and petroleum. Biomass contains little sulphur and nitrogen, so it does not produce the pollutants that can cause acid rain. Growing plants for use as biomass fuels may also help keep carbon dioxide levels balanced. Plants remove carbon dioxide-one of the greenhouse gases from the atmosphere when they grow.

Renewable resources

Renewable energy is energy which comes from natural resources such as sunlight, wind, rain, tides, and geothermal heat, which are renewable (naturally replenished) and the renewable power capacities with respect to years are represented on Figure 2.3. About 16% of global final energy consumption comes from renewables, with 10% coming from traditional biomass, which is mainly used for heating, and 3.4% from hydroelectricity. New renewables (small hydro, modern biomass, wind, solar, geothermal, and biofuels) accounted for another 3% and are growing very rapidly. (Renewables 2011: Global Status Report). The share of renewables in electricity generation is around 19%, with 16% of global electricity coming from hydroelectricity and 3% from new renewables, (Renewables 2011: Global Status Report).

Wind power is growing at the rate of 30% annually, with a worldwide installed capacity of 238 gig watts at the end of 2011, and is widely used in Europe, Asia, and the United States (Alex, 2011). At the end of 2011 the photovoltaic (PV) capacity worldwide was 67 GW, and PV power stations are popular in Germany and Italy. Solar thermal power stations operate in the USA and Spain, and the largest of these is the 354 megawatt (MW) SEGS power plant in the Mojave Desert. The world's largest geothermal power installation is the Geysers in California, with a muted capacity of 750 MW. Brazil has one of the largest renewable energy programs in the world, involving production of ethanol fuel from sugarcane, and ethanol now provides 18% of the country's automotive fuel Ethanol fuel is also widely available in the USA. (World Energy Assessment, (2001). While many renewable energy projects are large-scale, renewable technologies are also suited to natural and remote areas, where energy is often crucial in human development. As of 2011, small solar PV systems provide electricity to a few million households, and micro-hydro configured into mini-grids serves many more. Over 44 million households use biogas made in household-scale digesters for lighting and/or cooking and more than 166 million households rely on a new generation of more-efficient biomass cook stoves. According to United Nations Secretary-General Antonio Guterres, renewable energy has the ability to lift the poorest nations to new levels of prosperity. (Renewables, 2021).

Climate change concerns, coupled with high oil prices, peak of and increasing government support, are driving increasing renewable energy legislation, incentives and commercialization. New government spending regulation and policies helped the industry weather the global financial crisis better than many other sectors. According to a 2011 projection by the International Energy Agency, solar power generators may produce most of the world's electricity within 50 years, dramatically reducing the emissions of greenhouse gases that harm the environment (Adelekan, 2002).

Figure 3: Global renewable power capacity

Renewable energy flows involve natural phenomena such as sunlight, wind, tides, plant growth and geothermal heat, as the International Energy Agency explains that the renewable energy is derived from natural processes that are replenished constantly. In its various forms, it derives directly from the sun, or from heat enerated deep within the earth. Included in the definition is electricity and heat generated from solar, wind, ocean, hydropower, biomass, geothermal resources, and biofuels and hydrogen derived from renewable resources. (Renewables, 2010) Renewable energy provides 19% of electricity generation worldwide, Renewable power generators are spreading across many countries, and wind power alone already provides a significant share of electricity in some areas: for example, 14% in the US state of Iowa, 40% in the northern German state of Schleswig-Holstein, and 20% in Denmark. Some countries get most of their power from renewables, including Iceland and Paraguay (100%), Norway (98%), Bral (86%), Austria (62%), New Zealand (65%), and Sweden (54%) as reported in Renewables, (2010). Solar hot water makes an important contribution to renewable heat in many countries, most notably in China, which now has 70% of the global total (180 GWth). Most of these systems are installed on multi-family apartment buildings and meet a portion of the hot water needs of an estimated 50-60 million households in China. Worldwide, total installed solar water heating systems meet a portion of the water heating needs of over 70 million households. The use of biomass for heating continues to grow as well In Sweden, national use of biomass energy has surpassed that of oil. Direct geothermal for heating is also growing rapidly. Transport fueled renewable biofuels have contributed to a significant decline in oil consumption in the United States since 2006. The 93 billion litres of biofuels produced worldwide in 2009 displaced the equivalent of an estimated 68 billion litres of gasoline, equal to about 5% of world gasoline production (Schievano, et al, 2010).

Mainstream forms of Renewable Energy

The following energies are examples of renewable energy

- i. Wind power.
- ii. Hydro Power.
- iii. Solar Energy
- iv. Biomass

- v. Biofuels
- vi. Geothermal energy.

Non-Renewable Resources

A non-renewable resource is a natural resource which cannot be reproduced, grown, generated, or used on a scale which can sustain its consumption rate, once depleted there is no more available for future needs. Also considered non-renewable are resources that are consumed much faster than nature can create them. Fossil fuels (such as coal, petroleum, and natural gas), nuclear power (uranium) and certain aquifers are examples shown and on figure 2.4. In contrast, resources such as timber (when harvested sustainably) or metals (which can be recycled) are considered renewable resources. Natural resources such as coal, petroleum (crude oil) and natural gas take thousands of years to form naturally and cannot be replaced as fast as they are being consumed. Eventually natural resources will become too costly to harvest and humanity will need to find other sources of energy. Natural resources such as coal, petroleum (crude oil) and natural gas take thousands of years to form naturally and cannot be replaced as fast as they are being consumed. Eventually natural resources will become too costly to harvest and humanity will need to find other sources of energy (McClain et al, 2017).

U.S. primary energy consumption by energy source, 2020

total = 92.94 quadrillion British thermal units (Btu)

total = 11.59 quadrillion Btu

Source: U.S. Energy Information Administration, *Monthly Energy Review*, Table 1.3 and 10.1, April 2021, preliminary data
Note: Sum of components may not equal 100% because of independent rounding.

Figure 4: Examples of Energy sources. (www.wikipedia.org)

Production of biogas

Biogas is a gas that has a composition of about 50-70% Methane (CH₄), 30-50% Carbon dioxide (CO₂) with the remaining gases being hydrogen (H₂), dioxygen (O₂), hydrogen sulphide(H₂S), Nitrogen gas (N₂) and water vapour, generated from the anaerobic digestion of organic waste. To ensure optimal Bio-gas production, the three groups of micro-organisms must work together. In case of too much organic waste, the first and second groups of micro-organisms will produce a lot of organic acid which will decrease the pH of the reactor, making it unsuitable for the third group of micro-organisms. This will result in little or no gas production. On the other hand, if too little organic waste is present, the rate of digestion by micro-organisms will be minimal and production of Bio-gas will decrease significantly. Mixing could aid digestion in the reactor but,

too much mixing should be avoided as this would reduce bio-gas generation. Table 2.2 below shows the amount of biogas generated from animal waste and agriculture residue.

Figure 4 Amount of bio-gas generated from human solid waste and agriculture

The Process Anaerobic Digestion

Anaerobic biodegradation of organic material proceeds in the absence of oxygen and the presence of aerobic microorganisms. AD is the consequence of a series of metabolic interactions among various groups of microorganisms. It occurs in three stages, hydrolysis/liquefaction, acidogenesis and methanogenesis. The first group of microorganism secretes enzymes, which hydrolyses polymeric materials to monomers such as glucose and amino acids. These are subsequently converted by second group i.e. acetogenic bacteria to higher volatile fatty acids (H₂) and acetic acid. Finally, the third group of bacteria, methanogenic, convert H₂, CO₂, and acetate, to CH₄. These stages are described in detail below (Lombard, 2012). The AD is carried out in large digesters as shown in Figure 2.8 that are maintained at temperatures ranging from 30°C-65° C.

Figure 5: The digester at the Tilburg plant in Netherland.

Hydrolysis/liquefaction process

In the first stage of hydrolysis (figure 5), or liquefaction, fermentative bacteria convert the insoluble complex organic matter, such as cellulose, into soluble molecules such as sugars, amino acids and fatty acids. The complex polymeric matter is hydrolysed to monomer, e.g., cellulose to sugars or alcohols and proteins to peptides or amino acids, by hydrolytic enzymes. (Lipases,

proteases, celluloses, amylases, etc.) Secreted by microbes. The hydrolytic activity is of significant importance in high organic waste and may become rate limiting some industrial operations overcome this limitation by the use of chemical reagents to enhance hydrolysis. The application of chemicals to enhance the first step has been found to result in a shorter digestion time and provide a higher methane yield (RISE-AT, 1998). Below are examples of Hydrolysis/Liquefaction reactions: Lipids- Fatty Acids, Polysaccharides- Monosaccharides, Protein- Amino Acids, Nucleic Acids- Purines & Pyrimidines.

Acetogenesis process

This is the second stage (from figure 2.9), where an acetogenic bacteria, also known as acid formers, convert the products of the first phase to simple organic acids, carbon dioxide and hydrogen. The principal acids produced are acetic acid (CH₃COOH), propanoic acid (CH₃CH₂COOH), butanoic acid (CH₃CH₂COOH) and ethanol (C₂H₅OH). The products formed during acetogenesis are due to a number of different microbes, example, syntrophobacter Wolin, a propionate decomposer and surrophomon as wolf Ei, butyrate decomposer. Other acid formers are clostridium spp, peptococcusanerobus, and actinomyces. An acetogenesis reaction is shown below: C₆H₁₂O₆-2C₂H₅OH+2CO₂

Methanogenesis process

As seen in figure 5 also, the final and also the third page, methane is produced by bacteria called methane

formers (also known as methanogens) in two ways: either by means of cleavage of acetic acid molecules to generate carbon dioxide with hydrogen. Methane production is higher from reduction of carbon dioxide but limited hydrogen concentration in digester results in that the acetate action is the primary producer of methane (Omstead et al, 2018). The methanogenic bacteria include methanobacterium, methanobacillus, methanococcus and methanosarcina.

Methanogens can also be divided into two groups: acetate and H₂/CO₂consumers.

Methanosareina spp. and methanotrix spp. (also, methanosaeta) are considered to be important in AD both as acetate and H₂/CO₂ consumers.

The methanogenesis reaction can be expressed as follows:

Figure 5: Anaerobic Digestion Diagram. (Naskco Environment, 2009)

General Process Description

Generally, the overall anaerobic digestion process can be divided into four stages: Pre-treatment, waste digestion, gas recovery and residue treatment. Most digestion systems require pre-treatment of waste to obtain homogeneous feedstock. The pre-processing involves separation of non-digestible materials and shredding. The waste received by anaerobic digester is usually source separated or mechanically sorted. The separation ensures removal of undesirable or recyclable materials such as glass, metal, stones etc. In source separation, recyclables are removed from the organic wastes at the source. Mechanical separation can be employed if source separation is not available. However, the resultant fraction is then more contaminated leading to lower compost quality (RISE-AT, 1998).

The waste is shredded before it is fed into the digester. Inside the digester, the feed is diluted to achieve desired solids content and remains in the digester for a designated retention time. For dilution, a varying range of water sources can be used such as clean water, sewage sludge, or recirculated liquid from the digester effluent. A heat exchanger is usually required to maintain temperature in the digesting vessel (Figure 6). The biogas obtained in AD is scrubbed to obtain pipeline quality gas. In case of residue treatment, the effluent from the digester is dewatered, and the liquid recycled for use in the dilution of incoming feed. The bio solids are aerobically cured to obtain a compost product (Lincoln, 2019).

Figure 6: The flow diagram of low solids Anaerobic digestion

Benefit of Bio-Gas Technology

The following benefits will be obtained from bio-gas technology:

- (i) **Energy:** Biogas could be used as a fuel alternative to wood, oil, LPG and electricity
- (ii) **Agriculture:** The use of sludge from the bio-gas reactor could be used as compost. Organic nitrogen from waste will be transformed to ammonia nitrogen, a form of nitrogen which plants can uptake easily.
- (iii) **Protect environment:** Using bio-gas technology on animal waste treatment will reduce risk of infection from parasite and pathogenic bacteria inherent in the waste. Odour and flies will be significantly reduced in the area, and water pollution created by the dumping of waste can also be prevented.

METHODOLOGY

The materials used in this study include a biodigester tank prepared by excavating the ground in abattoir in Birnin Kebbi. Other materials include, gas storage bag as the airbag collection point, non-return valves, metal adaptor, length of hose pipe and four-inch pipe with some other materials, organic waste slurry from the abature. The following listed materials was used during the cause of this research work:

1. Animal slurry waste
2. Gas hose
3. Gas regulator
4. Blocks
5. Cement
6. 4inch waste pipe 6bar
7. Tire tube
8. Half inch pipe
9. Gas regulator
10. Adhesive (Resin & Hardener)

Method of construction

- i, Site preparation and marking - This is the selection of the location for the digester. It simply refers to making an assessment of making the right location for the construction of the digester tank.
- ii, Excavating the ground based on size of digester - This refers to the excavation of the location of the biodigester.
- iii, Laying of blocks to fit required size- This are process of constructing the air-tighter bio digester.
- iv. Covering the Bio-digester tank to seal Air Tight-This is to cover the tank with a precast Concrete slab and sealed with no space for ventilation.
- v. Assembling the fittings- This is the process of connecting the fittings by connecting the PVC pressure pipe and 4inch elbow from the inlet pipe to the digester to divert the solid waste from the inspection chamber to the digester and connection from the Bio-digester to the gas regulator by

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

using the half inch pipe from the digester to the Gas regulator for domestic use. This are connected by using 4-inch pressure PVC thick pipe, gas valve and adhesive (resin & hardener).

The study activities from week one - week six for a 110m³ space bio digester completion involving pre-development stage, construction stage and closure stage for this project are outlined in the Figure below.

Programme of work for the construction of biodigester

FINDINGS

Findings from the study indicates that Integrated waste management (IWM) strategies in public buildings offer significant benefits for the production of sustainable energy, specifically biogas, by treating organic waste on-site. The process, known as **anaerobic digestion**, converts organic waste like food scraps, animal waste and other materials into biogas and a nutrient-rich byproduct called digestate.

Some of the key benefits include;

- **Waste-to-Energy Conversion:** A primary benefit is transforming waste from a liability into a valuable resource. Public buildings like schools, hospitals, and government offices generate substantial amounts of organic waste. IWM diverts this waste from landfills, where it would produce methane—a potent greenhouse gas—and instead captures the methane in a controlled environment to produce biogas. This biogas can be used for electricity generation, heating, or cooking, helping to power the building itself and reducing reliance on fossil fuels.
- **Cost Reduction:** By processing waste on-site, public buildings can significantly reduce waste collection and disposal costs. This is particularly true for high-density urban areas where landfill fees and transportation costs are high. The revenue or cost savings from using the generated biogas can further offset the initial investment in the IWM system.

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

- **Environmental and Health Improvements:** IWM and biogas production reduce the volume of waste sent to landfills, conserving valuable land. This also mitigates the release of harmful methane emissions. The process of anaerobic digestion can also kill pathogens and reduce the unpleasant odors associated with decomposing organic waste, improving local air quality and sanitation. The liquid and solid byproduct, **digestate**, can be used as a natural fertilizer, replacing synthetic chemical fertilizers and enriching soil.
- **Promoting a Circular Economy:** The system creates a closed-loop or circular economy model. Waste from a building's kitchen, for example, is processed to produce energy and fertilizer, which can then be used on the building's grounds or in local agriculture. This model shifts away from a linear "take-make-dispose" approach to one that prioritizes resource recovery and reuse.
- **Educational and Public Relations Value:** For public buildings, implementing such a system can serve as a visible commitment to sustainability. It can be used as an educational tool for students and the public, demonstrating the principles of waste management, renewable energy, and environmental stewardship. It enhances the institution's public image and fosters community engagement.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

There was a significant expansion in the constructed biodigester container after 5 days which shows that anaerobic digestion has taking place without leakages. Gas produced from the digester were passed through filtering process as bubbles was noticed and the gas tank started expanding which indicate the experiment was successful without leakages.

From this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- i. The Bio-digester designed and constructed should be place in an environment exposed to sunlight.
- ii. The Bio-digester tank was test run using water to check for leakages.
- iii. The digestion of the slurry was done anaerobically (in the absence of oxygen) air tight close system.

The following are thus recommended:

- i. There should be a total retrofitting in the process of managing biodegradable waste in the abattoir to eliminate the spreading of diseases and contamination of meat for human consumption.
- ii. The biogas project work can also be done in large scale since its biproduct can generate income to manage the abattoir effectively.
- iii. The use of barricade fencing should be made to create a barrier to restrict access to project site.

SUGGESTION FOR FURTHER STUDIES

A further study should be carried out within the Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic Birnin Kebbi, using human bio degradable generated waste for renewable energy to augment it biogas production.

REFERENCE

- Abad, V., Avila, R., Vincent, T. & Front, X. (2019). 2019 Bioresource technology, 283, 10-17.
- Abubakar & Ismail (2012), *Combustion Characteristics and Energy Potential of Municipal Solid Waste in Arusha City – Tanzania*. 6th International Conference on appropriate technology, Kenyatta University Conference Centre, Nov. 2014, Nairobi, Kenya.
- Akhator, P. Obano., D I (2016). Thermal analysis of a small scale solid waste. *Nigerian Journal of Technology*, 35(3), 551-561.
- Akhator, P., Obanor, A., & Ugege, A. (2017) Nigerian Wood Waste: A Potential Resource for Economic Development. *Journal of Applied Science and Environmental Management*, 21(5), 246-251
- Alvarez, R. and Liden, G. (2009) *Semi-Continuous Co-Digestion of Solid Slaughterhouse waste, manure, Fruit and Vegetable Waste*. *Renewable Energy*, 33, 726-734
- Biogas – Africa (2008), *African Journal of Biotechnology*. Vol.8 (2), PP,116-125
- Botheju. D and Bakke. R (2011): Oxygen effects in Anaerobic digestion, *The open waste management journal*, V 4,1-19
- Braber, K (1995) Anaerobic Digestion of Municipal Waste: A Modern Waste Disposal Option on the Verge of Breakthrough. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 9. 365-376
- Dauda, M and Osita O.O. (2009) “Solid Waste Management and re-use in Maiduguri, Nigeria. *Proc of the 29th WEDC Int.Conf. towards the millennium development goals, Abuja*. PP.30 – 36, 2003
- Duerr, M., S., Cruden, A, McDonald, J. (2018). Energy and Power - [ttp://strathprints.strath.ac.uk](http://strathprints.strath.ac.uk)
- EESI (2009), Environmental and Energy Study Institute, *Biogas Capture and Utilisation: An effective, Affordable way to reduce greenhouse gas emission*. Issue Brief. June 2009
- Holm-Nielsen, J.B. (2009) The Future of Anaerobic Digestion and Biogas Utilization. *Bioresource Technology* 100, 5478-5484
- Ikuponisi. F.S (2014), Status of Renewable Energy in Nigeria. *Paper Presented at an International Conference on making renewable energy a reality, Abuja/ Port Harcourt/Calabar*
- Julius N. Fobil and Kothari (2005) *76 Int. J. Environmental Technology and Management, Vol 5, No. 1, Bioresource Technology* 100, 5478-5484
- Kathiravale S. & Yunus M. (2008) *Municipal solid waste: The Economic Opportunity*. Asia Europe Journal.

- Kothari, R., Tyagi, V. V & Pattiak, A. (2008). Waste to Energy: A way from renewable energy sources to sustainable development. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 143164_3170
- Kothari, C. R. (2014). *Research Methodology, Methods and Techniques* (2nd Ed)., pp.109-110). New Age, International Limited.
- Laura A. Pellegrini. *Chemical Engineering Transaction Vol. 43, 2015*
- Liu Y., Kuang Y., Huang N., Wu Z., and Xu L. (2008) *Renewable Energy* 33(9), 2027-2035.
- Matevz, O. & Matjaž, D., (2011), *Biogas – A Sustainable Energy Source: New possibilities and measures for Slovenia. JET Volume 4. P.P.11 – 24*
- Michaels. T, (2014), *Directory of waste to energy facilities, Energy Recovery Council.*
- Monnet.F (2003), *An Introduction to Anaerobic Digestion of Organic Waste. Final report by remade Scotland initiative.*
- National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy: *NREEP (2015)*, FEC approved copy for the electricity sector, Ministry of Power,
- Okey, E.J., Umana, A.A., Markson and Okey, P. A. (2013) *Municipal Solid Waste Characterization And Management Waste. WIT transactions on ecology and the environment, Vol 173(c) WIT press.*
- Okey FC-Onyesolu, (2018) *A review on waste to Biogas Sources and its potential in Nigeria. International Journal of Engineering & Technology* 7(4) 5960-5966
- Rodic.I, Scheiinberg.A, Wilson. D.C (2010), *Comparing Solid Waste Management in the World cities, in ISWA world Congress*
- Rupf, G. V., Bahri, P. A., De, B. K & Mchenry, M. P. (2016) *Broadcasting the potential of Biogas in Sub-Saharan Africa: An Assessment of Feasible Technologies & Feedstocks*
- Salman. Z, (2012) [http: WWW.bioenergyconsult.com](http://WWW.bioenergyconsult.com) for ' *Biomass from rice industry.*
- Sharvelle & Loestcher (2011) *Anaerobic Digestion of Animal Waste in Colorado.* Colorado State University Extension. *Statistical Review of World Energy* www.bp.com & www.worldometers.info
- Suberu M.Y., Mokhtar, A.S and Bashir, N. (2012) *Renewable Power Generation Opportunity From Municipal Solid Waste.* *Journal of Energy Technologies and Policy* 2(2)1-15.
- United Nations (2011) *Implementation of Bioenergy Systems towards Achieving United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals. Sustainability* (14), 38140

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

Voelker, B.M (2004), *Waste to Energy: Solutions for Solid Waste Problems for the 21st Century*.

Wang, J., Yuanyuan, W., Ynlin, Z. & Liang, M. (2009), *Biomass and Bioenergy* 33(5), Statistical Review of World Energy www.bp.com & www.worldometers.info 848-853.